

STEPS FOR IMPLEMENTATION OF COOPERATION BETWEEN
FAMILY, NEIGHBORHOOD AND EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS
IN THE SOCIALIZATION OF CHILDREN WITH DIFFICULT
DEVELOPMENT

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Annotation. *This article discusses the stages of the child's integration into society, the concept of socialization, the implementation of cooperation between the family, community, educational institution in the socialization of children with special needs.*

Keywords: *socialization, children with special needs, family, community, educational institution cooperation, personal development, spiritual and moral maturity, preparation for independent living.*

Introduction. On the basis of the reforms carried out in our country, it is planned to bring up a harmoniously developed person, to bring him up, to form a healthy mind, to develop him as a strong-willed, independent-minded person. The Development Strategy of the new Uzbekistan prioritizes the education of physically healthy, mentally and intellectually developed, independent-minded, loyal to the Fatherland, strong-minded outlook, deepening democratic reforms and increasing their social activity in the development of civil society. 'complaints are marked. Spiritual enrichment of the minds of our students, the development of independent and free thinking is the formation of the family, community, in the process of continuing education.

The main part. Socialization is the broadest concept among the processes that characterize an individual's education. It includes not only the development of the child's ready forms and methods of social life, ways of communicating with material and spiritual culture, adaptation to society, but also the development of social experience itself, value orientations, his lifestyle (with adults and peers). 'z includes. Education is a system of purposeful, pedagogically organized interactions between adults and children, with children. In such personal relationships there is a change in the motivational and value system of the child's personality, there is an opportunity to provide children with socially important norms

and ways of behavior, so education is one of the main ways of organized socialization. The term "socialization" is applied to man by the American sociologist F. G. Guldins, who in 1887 used it in his book *The Theory of Socialization* in a modern sense: "to develop the social nature or character of man, to prepare human materials for social life".

Figure 1. The scheme of the child's socialization

The development and maturity of the individual is a complex and controversial process, in which the heredity (biological factor), the social environment, the purposeful education and, finally, the independent activity are important. In educating the younger generation to be well-mannered and loyal to the state symbols, special attention should be paid to their youth and character, because without them the goal of education cannot be achieved. The Concept of Family, Neighborhood, School Cooperation, developed in 1993 to unite the efforts of the participants in the educational process, has become a well-known program for coordinating the activities of the general public in educating young people to be loyal to the ideas of independence, spiritually harmonious and patriotic.

The effectiveness of family, community, and school collaboration is enhanced by following these steps:

- working units of the participants of the process of cooperation in the field of education and upbringing;
- Harmony of respect and demand for the pupil;
- Equality and high responsibility of the subjects of the cooperation process;
- priority of national and state interests in the process of activity;
- scientific basis of cooperation.

The first stage. Working with young families. It is important to give young parents a philosophical, medical, understanding of the child and his upbringing, and to establish a "School of Young Mothers and Fathers" with the involvement of medical staff, reputable women and parents in these matters. reaches

The second stage. Drawing, storytelling, self-service, letter recognition, singing and dancing, various games to ensure the physical,

mental and spiritual development of the child in preschool to organize the work of pre-school groups "Sunday schools" to inculcate the concepts of conscious participation and the formation of skills for independent learning.

The third stage. Ensuring the physical, spiritual and social development of children at an early age (6-11) in school, identifying their initial talents and mental abilities, fostering a sense of responsibility for their own actions, the proper organization of leisure time to teach to do, to have a conscious attitude to the environment, to form feelings of friendship, internationalism, patriotism.

Step Four. Involvement of adolescents (11-16) in social activities, taking into account their interests, thirst for knowledge and intelligence, ensuring physical fitness, orientation to various professions through domestic work activities, o between groups of adolescents and the public Helping them to find their place, forming a sense of responsibility to society, the law and their parents for their actions, preparing them for social activism and building an independent family.

The fifth stage. Ensuring that young people (16 years and older) receive world-class education, choose a career, and prepare for independent living. To create conditions for them to get an education at the level of their abilities, to be employed in their chosen profession, to be economically independent. To fully form a sense of responsibility to fulfill the civic duties to the motherland, state and society, to prepare for an independent family.

To strengthen the focus on education and upbringing, to effectively implement the laws and documents adopted by our government in this regard, directives, the activities of the family, community, educational institution have a unique pedagogical system, methods and forms. 'must be. On the one hand, the events are thorough, so that the participants are pedagogically and psychologically integrated, logical, deep, interesting and visual, impressive, popular, practically short and concise, aesthetically wide need The collaborative work should involve all young people and citizens in the neighborhood and be in line with their interests and aspirations. Themes of cooperation events are "For a healthy generation", "Thanks to your parents", "Ball of etiquette", "Healthy mind in a healthy body", "Fountain of love", "Girls' prayer", "Forty trades for a young man", "My son is my guardian", "Life is a teacher, people are a teacher", "Uzbekistan is my homeland!" may include activities such as The established community council reports to the community on a quarterly

basis. If necessary, listening to the reports of educational institutions, community activists, organizations, enterprises and agencies located in the neighborhood on the work carried out in the field of education, providing them with financial and theoretical assistance is positive for the effectiveness and consistency of work affects.

Conclusion. Usually, all children have a problem with their parents from birth. But what is a problem for some is not a problem for others, and it depends on many factors. The attitude of the parents towards the child, the value system in the family, the presence or absence of relationships between family members, as well as many other things are the skills to overcome the difficulties that inevitably arise in the process of raising a child. Determines As A.S.Makarenko noted, a child with a difficult upbringing is a child, and his development is governed by general laws, the causes of some of these developmental disorders should be sought in the family and in school life in kindergarten and upbringing errors. In pedagogy, much attention is paid to the study of this issue. One of the hallmarks of a child's ability to reason on whether or not his or her upbringing is difficult or not is that he or she does not recognize the general means of pedagogical influence. The child does not listen to the simple suggestions and demands of the educator. He is stubborn. We believe that by increasing the effectiveness of targeted and targeted work carried out in partnership with the family, community and school, it is possible to socialize children with special needs, to develop them as individuals with a place in society.

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